

**TAXES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, THEIR
COMPOSITION AND SIGNIFICANCE.**

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Annotation. Tax is a compulsory, individually non-refundable payment levied on organizations and individuals in the form of alienation of funds owned by them in order to financially support the activities of the state and municipalities. Their functional meaning is to provide financial support for the domestic and foreign policies implemented by the state and to ensure the normal functioning of society.

The collection of taxes is regulated by tax legislation. The totality of the established taxes, as well as the principles, forms and methods of their establishment, amendment, cancellation, collection and control, constitute the tax system of the state. Tax is understood as a compulsory withdrawal of money from natural and legal persons by the state tax authorities, which is necessary for the state to carry out its functions.

All taxes are legislated by the state. The main document in the field of taxation is the Tax Code. It defines the basis of the tax system in the country. The tax authorities in Uzbekistan are represented by the State Tax Service (STS). It is an independent agency under the government, which has its own territorial divisions. The main task of the tax authorities is to control the accuracy of calculation, timeliness and completeness of tax payments to the state budget. In addition to tax control, the duties of tax authorities include free advice to taxpayers on all issues related to the application of tax legislation. Therefore, a person may always come to a branch of the STS and ask a question of interest.

Key words. Tax, financially support, functional meaning, necessary, tax services.

Main part. Today, Uzbekistan's economic model is not unreasonably ranked as one of the most stable and dynamic in the world. Over the past five years, Uzbekistan's gross domestic product has grown at an average rate of 8%, which is higher than the CIS average. In the years of independence, the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been reformed radically, in proportion to the development of the country's economy, and taxes that incorporate national traditions and best international practices are now in force.

Large-scale tax reforms have been implemented in the tax system, contributing to the growth of real income of the population, serving as a basis for modernization of production, and supporting small businesses and private entrepreneurship. Especially, the process of liberalization of the budget and tax system has become an important factor in the sustainable development of our economy.

While in 1991 the tax burden was 41.2% of the gross domestic product, it has been almost halved in recent years as a result of a rational policy. Thanks to the optimization of tax rates and implementation of a simplified taxation procedure, the index is now today, the ratio stands at 20,8%.

The tax system and its elements are presented in detail in the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Under Article 23 of the Tax Code, the following taxes and other compulsory payments apply on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan compulsory payments: 1. Taxes include:

- a) corporate income tax;
- b) personal income tax
- c) value-added tax;
- d) excise tax;
- e) taxes and special payments for subsoil users:
 - tax on subsoil use;
 - tax on excess profits;
 - bonuses (subscription and commercial discovery).
- f) tax on the use of water resources;

- g) property tax;
- h) land tax;
- i) tax on the improvement and development of social infrastructure;
- j) tax on the consumption of petrol, diesel fuel and gas for tax on the consumption of petrol, diesel fuel and gas for motor vehicles.

2. Other compulsory payments include:

(a) Mandatory payments to social funds:

- unified social payment;
- insurance contributions of citizens to the non-budgetary Pension Fund;
- obligatory contributions to the non-budgetary Pension Fund;

b) obligatory contributions to the republican road fund:

- compulsory contributions to the Republic Road Fund;
- fees to the Road Fund;

c) Compulsory contributions to the extra-budgetary Fund for the reconstruction, refurbishment and provision of equipment for secondary schools, vocational colleges, academic lyceums and medical facilities

d) State dues;

e) customs dues;

f) fee for the right to retail trade in certain types of goods and provision of certain types of services

In the cases and in the manner prescribed by the tax code

The following taxes payable under the simplified taxation procedure may be applied:

- single tax payment;
- single land tax;
- Single tax; single land tax; flat tax on certain types of entrepreneurial activity

As indicated, there are two types of taxation procedure in the country, namely: general and simplified system. Large enterprises pay taxes based on the general system,

while small enterprises and producers of agricultural goods pay a simplified (single) tax instead of several taxes and mandatory payments.

The taxes in force not only provide sufficient financial resources for the state budget, but also stimulate the development of entrepreneurial activity in the country. The existing taxes not only provide sufficient financial resources for the state budget, but also encourage the development of entrepreneurial activity in the country.

Conclusion. The modernization of Uzbekistan's economy in recent years, aimed at creating favourable conditions for business entities, facilitating their activities and further strengthening guarantees for their rights and freedoms, including in the area of taxation, has created a favourable environment for the development of entrepreneurship and the It has created a favourable environment for the development of entrepreneurship and the strengthening of its position.

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